

north american
academic research

North American Academic Research

THE WORLD
ASSOCIATION OF
SCIENTISTS &
PROFESSIONALS

Journal homepage: <http://twasp.info/journal/home>

Research

A Review of the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement of secondary school students

Tanzina Akter^{1*}

¹Master of Social Science, National University, Bangladesh

***Corresponding author**

Accepted: 30 January, 2020; **Online:** 4 February, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3637680>

Abstract: This paper audits the examination writing on the connection between parental association (PI) and scholastic accomplishment, with exceptional spotlight on the optional school (center and secondary school) level. The outcomes first present how singular PI factors correspond with scholastic accomplishment and afterward move to progressively complex examinations of numerous factors on the general build portrayed in the writing. A few PI factors with relationships to scholarly accomplishment show guarantee: (a) correspondence among kids and guardians about school exercises and plans, (b) guardians holding elevated requirements/desires for their kids' tutoring, and (c) guardians utilizing a legitimate child rearing style. We end the outcomes area by talking about the discoveries considering the impediments of non experimental look into and the changed impacts of youngsters' versus guardians' points of view on scholastic accomplishment.

Keywords: Relation, father, mother, parents, children.

©TWASP, The World Association of Scientists & Professionals

1. Introduction

An important issue in identifying points of leverage in improving students' academic achievement is determining how and to what degree parental involvement (PI) affects student achievement. Such knowledge might inform parenting practices as well as school-based policies, practices, and interventions that involve working with parents. For example, such research might help in the design and development of interventions that maximize parental involvement, where it has been shown to have the most positive and powerful effect. To assist in this endeavor, we reviewed the literature about the types of PI that might have an impact. We found that the literature on PI is quite “knotty”—complex and sometimes contradictory. This paper attempts to disentangle the knot

by closely examining the current literature on the relationship between PI and academic achievement at the middle and high school levels.

The idea that parental involvement engenders students' academic achievement is intuitively appealing to the point that society in general, and educators in particular, have considered PI an important ingredient for the remedy of many ills in education today. In the 1980s and early 1990s, studies were published that suggested the importance of parental involvement in school. In the mid-1990s, the popular press, policy makers, and school administrators actively advocated PI. Legislation was enacted, such as the Goals 2000: Educate America Act and the reauthorized Elementary and Secondary Education Act (ESEA) in the United States, which has made parents' involvement in their children's education a national priority [1]. Schools have been encouraged to reexamine their parental involvement policies and programs and to demonstrate innovative approaches in order to obtain federal education dollars. For example, eligibility for Title I funding is now contingent on the development of agreements where families and schools assume mutual responsibility for children's learning.

Many practitioners and researchers support the policy direction of increased PI in their children's academic lives, yet confusion persists regarding an appropriate definition of PI and the activities, goals, and desired outcomes of various PI programs and policies. Less is known about PI than is commonly assumed. Early studies suggesting the importance of PI are, unfortunately, treated as definitive, regardless of the equivocal nature of the data, and they are used to support the position that virtually all types of PI are important. According to Sui-Chu and Willms [2], PI has been treated too long as a one-dimensional construct.

It is apparent that identifying the influence of PI on academic achievement is complicated by at least three factors: (a) researchers use different definitions for the PI construct, (b) there is a paucity of experimental studies in the PI research literature, and (c) mediating factors and interacting variables in the PI-academic achievement story are often ignored. Any effort to clarify the role of PI in academic achievement must consider these issues.

2. Purpose

This paper examines the research literature on the relationship between PI and academic achievement, with particular focus on the middle and high school level. Research has shown that

in addition to students' personal goals and expectations in this age group, other variables such as PI might exert considerable influence on the students' academic achievement and behavior [3–5].

This paper will examine how PI has been defined, describe the relationships between PI variables and academic achievement, attempt to generalize the results, and finally discuss key areas of controversy and areas for further research.

3. Methodology

3.1. Procedure

We began this literature review process by gathering and reviewing many books, reviews, meta-analyses, and individual articles relating to the PI literature. The following online databases were employed to search and collect these sources.

ERIC

A database that provides extensive access to educational-related literature from two printed journals: Resources in Education (RIE) and Current Index to Journals in Education (CIJE).

PsychInfo

An online version of Psychological Abstracts that covers journal articles, book chapters, books, technical reports, and dissertations in psychology and psychological aspects of related disciplines.

EBSCOhost

An online system that provides access to several periodical indexes or databases. These databases contain citations, abstracts and many full-text articles from magazines, journals, and newspapers. In addition to these databases, Google Scholar, the Brigham Library at Educational Testing Service, and the Strozier Library at the Florida State University were used to search for and acquire specific references. Google Scholar is a web site providing peer-reviewed papers, books, abstracts, and articles from academic publishers, professional societies, universities, and other scholarly organizations. The Brigham Library at Educational Testing Service and the Strozier Library at Florida State University both house comprehensive collections of educational, psychological, sociological, and testing literature.

3.2. Inclusion Criteria

The focus of the search was to access full-text documents using various search terms and keywords such as *parental involvement*, *parental influence*, *peer influence*, *personality*, *academic achievement*, and *parental involvement*. The search was not limited to a particular date range. From the large set of documents that we collected, a total of 74 documents met the criteria for inclusion in the literature review. The inclusion criteria consisted of topical relevance, focus on secondary education, and papers that presented results in terms of prominent PI variables. Additional inclusion criteria were papers that studied any mediating factors and interacting variables in the PI-student academic achievement relationship.

The majority of the documents we obtained were fifty individual studies reported in journal articles, book chapters, and research reports, followed by eight books, six longitudinal studies, five NELS:88 (i.e., the National Education Longitudinal Study of 1988, Institute of Education Sciences, n.d. [6]) reports, three extensive literature reviews, and two meta-analyses. We omitted qualitative studies and studies that did not meet the specified criteria.

3.3. Defining Parental Involvement

Figure 1 depicts the prominent aspects of PI found in the literature. We have grouped these variables into the two main categories of home and school activities.

Figure 1_

Prominent aspects of parental involvement enacted at home and at school.

Many studies examine underlying aspects of PI, yet few do it in exactly the same way [1]. Such differences make it difficult to assess cumulative knowledge across studies and can also lead to contradictory findings. We will point these out in the results section as they arise.

4. Literature Review Results

The results of the literature review are presented in terms of how PI variables impact student academic achievement, in two sections: (a) findings around single PI variables and (b) findings of large-scale studies that analyze the PI construct in terms of a set of underlying variables. Then, we discuss the findings in light of the limitations of nonexperimental research and the different effects of children's and parents' perspectives on academic achievement.

4.1. Single Parental Involvement Variables

In this section, we look at the results of different studies on prominent PI variables, including parent-child discussions about school, parental aspirations and expectations, parenting style, reading at home, checking homework, school involvement, and home rules and supervision.

4.2. Parent-Child Discussions about School

The parent-child discussion variable refers to ongoing conversations between parents and their children concerning school-related activities, programs, near- and long-term school plans, and other academic issues. This variable frequently yields the strongest positive association with academic achievement [2, 4, 7–11]. McNeal [4], for example, found that the only dimension of parental involvement that was associated with improved achievement and reduced problematic behavior (e.g., truancy) was parent-child discussion. Parent-child discussion has a significant relationship to student achievement (,) and a significant inverse relationship to truancy (,).

One interesting subtlety involving this variable is that talking with one's mother is positively associated with academic achievement, but the association between talking with one's father and academic achievement may depend on ethnicity and also on whether the child or parent is reporting [9, 12, 13]. For instance, talking with one's father shows no correlation to academic achievement when data are collapsed across ethnicities, but talking with fathers for Black and Hispanic children is negatively related to achievement, while for Asian children talking with fathers is positively related to achievement.

4.3. Parental Aspirations and Expectations

Parental aspirations and expectations are often described collectively or used interchangeably in the literature. Taken together, aspirations and expectations reflect the degree to which parents presume that their child will perform well in school, now and in the future. This variable appears in many PI research studies and is generally shown to have a positive relationship to academic achievement. For example, parental aspirations/expectations is the strongest dimension in the Fan and Chen [14] meta-analysis examining effects on academic achievement (overall), as well as the strongest predictor () in the Singh et al. [15]) structural equation modeling study. Parental expectations also has the largest effect size () and is one of the strongest predictors in determining academic achievement () in Jeynes' [10] meta-analysis on PI variables.

To date, of the PI papers we reviewed, the articles and large-scale studies that focus on parental expectations report a generally positive effect on student achievement. More specifically, Baker and Soden [1] note that high aspirations/expectations, coupled with an effective parenting style (i.e., moderate levels of parental support and supervision) are positively related to academic achievement. Similarly, Kurdek et al. [16] examined the relationship between parental supervision (measured via student report) and sixth-grade students' academic achievement. Their results showed a clear quadratic relationship (i.e., inverted U function) between these two variables, where the highest levels of achievement (measured by grade point average) were associated with *moderate* levels of parental supervision, while worse achievement related to both low and high levels of supervision respectively. We now turn our attention to research involving parenting style.

4.4. Parenting Style

This PI variable is defined as a complex set of behaviors and/or attitudes by which parents demonstrate and communicate the values, behaviors, and standards that their children are expected to adopt. According to various researchers [10, 17–20], parenting style may be viewed along two dimensions: responsive and demanding (see Figure 2).

		Responsive	
		Low	High
Demanding	Low	Indifferent	Permissive
	High	Authoritarian	Authoritative

Figure 2_

A cross of responsive and demanding parenting, yielding four distinct styles.

An *authoritative* parenting style is consistently and positively associated with student academic outcomes. This style is characterized by parents who are both responsive and demanding (lower right-hand corner of Figure 2). However, *authoritarian* and *permissive* styles (as well as *indifferent* styles) are negatively related to academic achievement [18, 21–24].

We examined 28 articles that studied parenting style in some form or another and its relationship to academic achievement. Representative characteristics of parenting style in the literature include authoritative style, joint decision making, PI in children’s lives, behavioral supervision, discussion of education with one’s children, firm disciplinary practices, permissive (or indifferent) styles,

limit setting, strong communication, and maternal and paternal styles. The following are mixed findings in the literature on the variable of parenting style.

4.5. Positive Association

Authoritative parenting style is characterized by parents who develop and maintain close, warm relationships with their children while at the same time establishing structure and guidelines that are enforced as necessary. This parenting style was referred to in seven articles. They all reported a positive association with student achievement [25–30], except for one study that showed no effect for first generation Chinese Americans [31]. Aunola et al. [26] similarly investigated the extent to which adolescents' achievement is associated with parenting styles in their families. They found that adolescents from authoritative families showed significantly greater achievement compared to other adolescents who experienced different parenting styles ().

In some studies, parental affective support appeared to be one of the strongest predictors of students' academic achievement. For example, in a study by Deslandes et al. [27], they reported that parental affective support was a strong predictor of school achievement for both males (,) and females (,). A child's perception of parenting style was referred to in one article, which reported that child perceptions of parenting style, involvement, and teacher/school communication factors strongly predicted school achievement (,) [30]. The recent meta-analysis conducted by Jeynes [10] showed a strong positive association () between parental style—defined as supportive, loving, helpful, and maintaining an adequate level of discipline—and academic achievement.

These positive associations may be due to the ability of parents with an authoritative parenting style to be loving and supportive and yet maintain an adequate level of discipline in the household. Parents with this parenting style also demonstrate qualities such as trust and approachability that motivate children to discuss academic problems and expectations with their parents. Additionally, such parents are more likely to make contact with teachers when students have academic or behavioral problems [10, 27].

4.6. No Association or Negative Association

PI in the form of behavioral supervision has shown either no association or a negative relationship with academic achievement [7]. For example, firm disciplinary practices were found to be

unrelated to a child's academic success [32], based on a sample of 59 6–11-year-old African Americans from homeless families. A survey with Korean American adolescents showed that differences in parenting styles did not significantly relate to adolescents' academic achievement [33]. And McNeal [4] showed that PI in the form of supervision generally explained behavioral outcomes (e.g., truancy) (,) but not cognitive outcomes (e.g., science achievement), and had greater effects for more affluent White students (,) than for less-advantaged students of any other race. This finding may be the result of minority parents feeling less comfortable getting involved in school-based activities and also being less likely to initiate meetings with school teachers when their child is facing an academic problem. Past negative experiences shape parents' involvement with educational institutions [4].

On the other hand, Deslandes et al. [28] and Chen [8] found a negative relationship between parental supervision and children's achievement. This negative association might be related to the fact that some parents increase their support/supervision when they become concerned with their children's underachievement. In other words, parents adopt strategies based on their children's academic performance [4, 8].

4.7. Other PI Variables

Fairly consistent associations between other PI variables and academic achievement include the following. (i) *School involvement*, which refers to participation in parent-teacher organizations (PTOs) or associations (PTAs), community involvement, volunteer work, and so on, has shown a positive association with academic achievement [11, 25]. For instance, Adeyemo [25] examined the effects of different parental involvement dimensions on academic achievement for 250 secondary school students and found that parental involvement in their child's school environment significantly affected students' academic achievement (,). (ii) *Parent-teacher communication*, described as parents' communication with teachers regarding their child's progress, has shown a positive association with students' academic achievement (,) [10]. (iii) *Parents checking child's homework*, has shown a positive association with academic achievement in some studies [10, 11]. For instance, Keith et al. [11] found that students whose parents were involved in checking their homework showed higher achievement () than students whose parents were not involved in checking homework. Other studies, however, have shown a negative association between parents

checking their children's homework and academic achievement [34].(iv)*Home supervision and rules*, refers to moderate levels of parental support [10, 16], and when combined with appropriate monitoring of home-related behaviors (such as television viewing) has shown positive associations with academic achievement [11, 35]. Children of parents who closely monitor their activities spend less time watching television and more time on school-related activities, which in turn shows a positive relationship with academic achievement () [11].(v)*Reading at home*, which reflects parental modeling and support of the child's reading along with the provision of a stimulating literacy environment, has shown a positive association with academic achievement [3, 11, 25, 36]. For example, in a study by Chen [3], the effect size () suggested a strong relationship between parental involvement in their child's reading at home and academic achievement ().

To summarize, there is seldom more than a small-to-moderate association between any individual PI variable and academic achievement. The strongest associations appear to be (a) discussions about school activities between parent and child (positive), (b) parents' aspirations/expectations for their children (positive), and (c) parental styles, particularly authoritative style (positive) and authoritarian and permissive styles (negative).

While each of the PI variables presented in this section has shown some relationship to students' academic achievement, it is also clear from recent research that the effects are complex. For instance, studies have found interactions between some of these PI variables and academic engagement/involvement (e.g., time spent on homework and paying attention in class), ethnicity, race, family structure, family characteristics (such as parents' education), maternal employment status, socioeconomic status, and gender [9–11, 13, 27, 37–40]. Consequently, we can view these as potentially moderating or mediating variables in relation to student achievement. For example, in a longitudinal study conducted by Dearing et al. [13] involving 167 children, the effect of PI on the children's academic achievement (i.e., reading) was moderated by maternal education. We now explore more complex analyses of the PI construct.

5. Conclusions

Parents appear to have an important opportunity to influence their children's academic achievement though the influence may not be as great as traditionally believed. Correlational studies have found modest associations between various PI variables and student academic

achievement, with some of the most consistent relationships being reported for (a) parents talking with their child about school [2, 4, 8–11, 50], (b) parents holding high expectations for students' academic achievement [1, 3, 10, 14], and (c) parents employing an authoritative (not authoritarian) parenting style [10, 17, 19, 20]. Citing the inability of correlational studies to determine causality, as well as the findings of twin and adoption studies, researchers have estimated the impact of PI variables on academic achievement as quite modest [44, 47–49]. Others have agreed that the influence of parents is modest but go on to assert that peer influence is likewise modest [47]. It seems that both parents and peers can have an influence on a child's academic achievement.

Given that parents have limited influence over the child's peer relationships, direct parental influence remains an opportunity to leverage those factors for the benefit of the child, including their academic achievement. The design of policies, practices, and interventions should reflect an understanding of these findings about the nature and magnitude of parental influence on children's academic achievement.

References

1. A. J. L. Baker and L. M. Soden, "ED419030 1998-04-00 the challenges of parent involvement research," Tech. Rep. ERIC/CUE Digest Number 134, ERIC Clearinghouse on Urban Education, New York, NY, USA, 1998. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
2. E. H. Sui-Chu and J. D. Willms, "Effects of parental involvement on eighth-grade achievement," *Sociology of Education*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 126–141, 1996. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
3. H-F. Chen, *The longitudinal factor structure of parent involvement and its impact on academic achievement: findings from the ECLS-K dataset*, ProQuest Dissertations, University of Denver, Denver, Colo, USA, 2009.
4. R. B. McNeal, "Parental involvement as social capital: differential effectiveness on science achievement, truancy, and dropping out," *Social Forces*, vol. 78, no. 1, pp. 117–144, 1999. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
5. E. N. Patrikakou, "Adolescence: are parents relevant to high school students' achievement," FINE network at Harvard Family Research Project,

2004, <http://www.gse.harvard.edu/hfrp/projects/fine/resources/digest/adolescence.html>. View at: [Google Scholar](#)

6. Institute of Education Sciences. (n.d.), “National Longitudinal Study of 1988,” National Center for Educational Statistics Web site, <http://nces.ed.gov/surveys/nels88/>. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
7. S. Catsambis, “Expanding knowledge of parental involvement in secondary education: effects on high school academic success,” Tech. Rep. 27, Johns Hopkins University, Center for Research on the Education of Students Placed at Risk, Baltimore, Md, USA, 1998. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
8. J. J. L. Chen, “Grade-level differences: relations of parental, teacher and peer support to academic engagement and achievement among Hong Kong students,” *School Psychology International*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 183–198, 2008. View at: [Publisher Site](#) | [Google Scholar](#)
9. L. Desimone, “Linking parent involvement with student achievement: do race and income matter?” *Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 93, no. 1, pp. 11–30, 1999. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
10. W. H. Jeynes, “The relationship between parental involvement and urban secondary school student academic achievement: a meta-analysis,” *Urban Education*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 82–110, 2007. View at: [Publisher Site](#) | [Google Scholar](#)
11. T. Z. Keith, P. B. Keith, G. C. Troutman, P. G. Bickley, P. S. Trivette, and K. Singh, “Does parental involvement affect eighth-grade student achievement? Structural analysis of national data,” *School Psychology Review*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 474–496, 1993. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
12. J. Battle, “Longitudinal analysis of academic achievement among a nationwide sample of Hispanic students in one- versus dual-parent households,” *Hispanic Journal of Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 430–447, 2002. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
13. E. Dearing, K. McCartney, H. B. Weiss, H. Kreider, and S. Simpkins, “The promotive effects of family educational involvement for low-income children's literacy,” *Journal of School Psychology*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 445–460, 2004. View at: [Publisher Site](#) | [Google Scholar](#)
14. X. Fan and M. Chen, “Parental involvement and students' academic achievement: a meta-analysis,” *Educational Psychology Review*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1–22, 2001. View at: [Publisher Site](#) | [Google Scholar](#)

15. K. Singh, P. G. Bickley, P. S. Trivette, T. Z. Keith, P. B. Keith, and E. S. Anderson, "The effects of four components of parental involvement on eighth grade student achievement: Structural analysis of NELS-88 data," *School Psychology Review*, vol. 24, pp. 299–317, 1995. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
16. L. A. Kurdek, M. A. Fine, and R. J. Sinclair, "School adjustment in sixth graders: parenting transitions, family climate, and peer norm effects," *Child Development*, vol. 66, no. 2, pp. 430–445, 1995. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
17. D. Baumrind, "Current patterns of parental authority," *Developmental Psychology*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–103, 1971. View at: [Publisher Site](#) | [Google Scholar](#)
18. E. E. Maccoby, "Parenting and its effects on children: on reading and misreading behavior genetics," *Annual Review of Psychology*, vol. 51, pp. 1–27, 2000. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
19. E. E. Maccoby and J. A. Martin, "Socialization in the context of the family: parent-child interaction," in *Handbook of Child Psychology, Socialization, Personality and Social Development*, P. H. Mussen and E. M. Hetherington, Eds., vol. 4, pp. 1–101, John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY, USA, 4th edition, 1983. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
20. S. E. Paulson, "Relations of parenting style and parental involvement with ninth-grade students' achievement," *Journal of Early Adolescence*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 250–267, 1994. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
21. D. Baumrind, "Parental disciplinary patterns and social competence in children," *Youth & Society*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 239–251, 1978. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
22. D. H. Demo and M. J. Cox, "Families with young children: a review of research in the 1990s," *Journal of Marriage and Family*, vol. 62, no. 4, pp. 876–895, 2000. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
23. S. M. Dornbusch, P. L. Ritter, P. H. Leiderman, D. F. Roberts, and M. J. Fraleigh, "The relation of parenting style to adolescent school performance," *Child Development*, vol. 58, no. 5, pp. 1244–1257, 1987. View at: [Google Scholar](#)
24. B. Radziszewska, J. L. Richardson, C. W. Dent, and B. R. Flay, "Parenting style and adolescent depressive symptoms, smoking, and academic achievement: ethnic, gender, and SES

differences,” *Journal of Behavioral Medicine*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 289–305, 1996. View at: [Publisher Site](#) | [Google Scholar](#)

25. D. A. Adeyemo, “Parental involvement, interest in schooling and school environment as predictors of academic self-efficacy among fresh secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria,” *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 163–180, 2005.

Tanzina Akter

Master of Social Science, National University, Bangladesh

Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. *TWASP, NY, USA*. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

